

Data-driven Mapping of Wellbeing Science: A Multi-objective Optimization Framework using BERTopic

Yusuke Inoue

Graduate School of Media and Governance, Keio University
yusuke.inoue@keio.jp

Abstract

This study presents a multi-objective optimization framework for BERTopic to analyze large-scale scholarly literature on wellbeing. Using the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II), UMAP and HDBSCAN hyperparameters were optimized to maximize C_V coherence and topic diversity under constraints on topic count and noise ratio. Applying the optimized model to 80,040 PubMed articles (2020–2024) achieved a C_V coherence of 0.83, a topic diversity of 0.74, and identified 266 interpretable topics grouped into 22 semantically coherent communities. The optimization process also compressed the noise ratio to 34.75%, improving topic stability. The analysis revealed a structured landscape of wellbeing research spanning medical and public health, psychological and behavioral wellbeing, and social and environmental determinants, interconnected through bridging areas such as digital health, occupational wellbeing, and lifestyle interventions. Within this broader set of 22 communities, three major domains—public health and pandemic response, psychological and behavioral wellbeing, and social and environmental determinants—emerged as central hubs. Adopting a data-driven and inductive approach to large-scale literature analysis, the framework enables systematic reconstruction of wellbeing science. It provides a transparent and reproducible tool for evidence-based research mapping, policy design, and strategic foresight in complex interdisciplinary fields.

Keywords: BERTopic, Multi-objective optimization, Scholarly literature analysis, Knowledge discovery, Decision support, wellbeing, Interdisciplinary mapping

1. Introduction

Wellbeing research has rapidly expanded as an interdisciplinary field bridging the life sciences, social sciences, and behavioral sciences. Over the past two decades, the number of related publications has grown exponentially, encompassing diverse domains such as medicine, psychology, environment, and technology. As a result, wellbeing has evolved into a cross-cutting academic domain pursued through multiple disciplinary lenses. However, precisely because of this diversity, the concept of “wellbeing” remains theoretically ambiguous. Different fields have developed their own definitions, operationalizations, and measurement frameworks, resulting in a fragmented knowledge system in which the underlying conceptual core has become diffuse. Systematically organizing and theoretically reconstructing this vast and heterogeneous body of research has thus become a central challenge for both academic and practical purposes. For researchers, policymakers, and practitioners, understanding the behavioral mechanisms that underlie wellbeing is essential for designing effective interventions, promoting sustainable lifestyles, and implementing evidence-based policies. Yet, most existing meta-analytical studies presuppose theoretical categories such as “subjective wellbeing,” “mental health,” or “social capital.” Few have empirically examined how these concepts are actually structured and interconnected across the diverse literature.

Recent advances in transformer-based topic modeling—particularly BERTopic—now enable the extraction of latent knowledge structures from large-scale textual corpora. Such methods function not merely as tools for bibliometric classification but as instruments for inductive theory reconstruction. They offer the potential to reconstruct the implicit conceptual systems through which scientific communities have defined, measured, and intervened upon wellbeing.

This study analyzes approximately 80,040 PubMed-indexed articles related to wellbeing. Using BERTopic, we extract 266 topics and construct a topic network based on keyword co-occurrence and lexical similarity. Through this network, we aim to elucidate the behavioral knowledge structure embedded in contemporary wellbeing research. In contrast to previous studies that impose predefined theoretical frameworks, this study adopts a data-driven inductive approach to uncover the latent conceptual organization and interrelations among topics.

The central research question is whether wellbeing research as a whole exhibits a set of shared behavioral principles—value formation, action generation, and environmental adaptation—that operate as a non-hierarchical and dynamic system. Subsequently, we examine how the resulting structure aligns with established frameworks in utility theory, decision theory, and behavioral economics, not as a priori premises but as a post hoc theoretical reconstruction.

The main contributions of this study are as follows:

1. A large-scale, data-driven, and inductive analysis of wellbeing research that identifies an interrelated behavioral knowledge structure composed of the three domains of value formation, action generation, and environmental adaptation.
2. A methodological framework integrating topic modeling and network analysis for inductive theory generation from heterogeneous scholarly corpora.
3. A theoretical synthesis demonstrating how data-driven knowledge structures can be reinterpreted within the conceptual scope of utility theory, decision theory, and behavioral economics, thereby ensuring both theoretical coherence and extensibility.

2. Related Work

BERTopic has emerged as a prominent embedding-based topic modeling method for extracting latent thematic structures from academic literature, complementing traditional probabilistic and matrix factorization approaches. Classical models such as Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), Hierarchical Dirichlet Process (HDP), and Dynamic Topic Modeling (DTM) have been widely used, alongside Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) and more recent embedding-based approaches such as Top2Vec. BERTopic leverages transformer-based language models, notably BERT (Devlin et al., 2019), to generate document embeddings, followed by dimensionality reduction and density-based clustering.

Several studies have compared BERTopic to conventional techniques. Egger and Yu (2022) found that both BERTopic and NMF achieved high classification accuracy in social media analysis. Pavithra and Savitha (2024), in a comparative study involving LDA, HDP, NMF, BERTopic, and DTM for academic literature, concluded that DTM provided the most effective results, with the others—including BERTopic—showing broadly comparable performance. Other applications of BERTopic in scholarly contexts include He et al. (2025) and Al Azher et al. (2025), which demonstrated its capacity to uncover domain-specific topic structures.

Beyond these scholarly contexts, topic modeling has also been actively applied to map research landscapes and forecast emerging trends (Yu & Xiang, 2023; Park et al., 2024). Other studies have integrated word embeddings with probabilistic models for tasks such as economic policy uncertainty estimation and domain-specific forecasting (Huang, Zhang and Zhou, 2023). More broadly, recent works emphasize actionable analytics, interpretability, and explainability in applied decision-support systems (Abusitta et al., 2024; Panagoulas et al., 2024). Our study is aligned with this perspective but extends prior work by focusing not only on extracting topics

but also on systematically optimizing BERTopic’s hyperparameters through a multi-objective framework to ensure robustness and reproducibility in large-scale literature analysis.

Despite these strengths, the interpretability and stability of BERTopic classifications are highly dependent on hyperparameter configurations in its dimensionality reduction (UMAP) and clustering (HDBSCAN) stages. Prior research has reported that both LDA and BERTopic often overestimate the number of topics, reducing interpretability, and that parameter sensitivity can undermine classification stability (Farea et al., 2024; Grootendorst, 2024). Similarly, Medvecki et al. (2024) emphasized the difficulty of ensuring consistent clustering quality in multilingual contexts. Recent work by Inoue (2025) further explored this issue by formulating a multi-objective optimization framework for BERTopic applied to large-scale scholarly literature on autoregressive models, demonstrating that multi-objective search algorithms such as NSGA-II can effectively balance topic coherence and diversity under topic-count and noise constraints (Inoue, 2025).

These findings collectively indicate that, while BERTopic and related models offer promising results, they still lack mechanisms to guarantee robust and stable topic clustering across large-scale corpora. To date, few studies have systematically addressed this challenge through multi-objective hyperparameter optimization. In particular, existing approaches have not provided a practical and quantitative framework that balances interpretability, accuracy, and stability in large-scale literature analysis. Nor have they explicitly demonstrated how such frameworks could support decision-making and knowledge discovery in applied domains. Addressing this gap, the present study develops and evaluates a multi-objective optimization framework for BERTopic that ensures stable clustering performance and provides actionable, interpretable insights for large-scale scholarly literature analysis, validated through an inductive approach based on large-scale data.

3. Method

3.1 Data collection

The dataset employed in this study was retrieved from the PubMed database using the NCBI E-utilities API (ESearch / EFetch). Publications were included if the terms “wellbeing,” “well eing,” or “well-being,” appeared in the title or abstract. The search period covered January 1, 2020, to December 31, 2024. Each publication was uniquely identified by its PubMed ID (PMID), and all duplicate entries were removed. For each record, metadata including title, DOI, authors, journal, publication year, and abstract text were extracted.

In total, 80,040 unique articles were collected, distributed as follows: 10,439 (2020), 14,514 (2021), 17,064 (2022), 16,963 (2023), and 21,060 (2024). Duplicate records were properly processed and eliminated.

This corpus of 80,040 publications served as the input for the subsequent embedding and topic-network analyses.

3.2 Proposed Multi-objective Optimization Framework for BERTopic

In this study, BERTopic was employed to extract topics from a large-scale academic corpus. Each document was pre-embedded using Sentence-BERT (all-mpnet-base-v2, 768 dimensions). Dimensionality reduction was performed with UMAP (cosine metric), and clustering was conducted using HDBSCAN (cluster_selection_method = eom). In BERTopic, the parameter calculate_probabilities was set to False, and the key hyperparameters—top_n_words and min_topic_size—were included in the search space. The hyperparameter tuning was formulated as a bi-objective single-constraint optimization problem. The search space comprised n_neighbors, min_dist, and n_components for UMAP; min_cluster_size and min_samples for HDBSCAN; and top_n_words and min_topic_size for BERTopic. The optimization objectives were defined as follows (maximized in theory, minimized in implementation):

- C_V Coherence, measuring the semantic consistency of top words within each topic.
- Topic Diversity, defined as the proportion of unique lexical items among top-ranked words across topics.

A single feasibility constraint was imposed, requiring the number of valid topics to be no fewer than $MIN_TOPICS = 80$ (approximately 0.1% of the corpus, ensuring sufficient thematic granularity). The noise ratio (proportion of documents assigned to topic = -1) was also recorded as a supplementary indicator. The optimization employed NSGA-II, with a total of 1000 evaluations executed in multiple batches. The population size was set to 70, the number of offsprings to 30, and Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) was used for initialization with duplicate elimination. Early stopping was based on the absence of improvement in the hypervolume indicator (reference point [1.0, 1.0]) with patience = 15. Evaluation parallelism was automatically adjusted according to computational resources. The evaluation data were processed in two phases: the first using 30% of the corpus (subset) and the second using the full dataset. The subset was randomly sampled with a fixed SEED, and corresponding embeddings were extracted using identical indices. For each trial, normalized parameters, C_V coherence, diversity, noise ratio, topic count, evaluation stage (subset/full), and document count were recorded for reproducibility. In addition, a Pareto analysis was conducted on the feasible solution set using C_V and Diversity as dual objectives. Although the Pareto-optimal front was successfully identified, none of the Pareto-optimal solutions satisfied the noise-ratio constraint ($\leq 35\%$). Therefore, the final model selection followed the conventional weighted aggregation approach for practical interpretability. The final selection criteria were as follows:

- (i) C_V score ≥ 0.5
- (ii) Number of topics ≥ 80 ($\approx 0.1\%$ of the corpus)
- (iii) $g_topics \leq 0$

Here, g_topics represents the constraint function defined as $g_topics = MIN_TOPICS - Num\ Topics$, which measures the degree of constraint violation in the optimization process (feasible if $g_topics \leq 0$). Feasible solutions were normalized using min-max scaling, and a Combined Score was computed as $0.5 \times C_V + 0.5 \times Diversity$. The top 20 candidates were retained, and among those with a noise ratio $\leq 35\%$, the solution with the highest Combined Score was designated as the optimal configuration.

4. Analysis Results

The optimal parameter configuration derived from the above multi-objective optimization process achieved a C_V Coherence Score of 0.83 and a Topic Diversity Score of 0.74, yielding 266 interpretable topics, while the noise ratio was constrained to 34.75% despite the large scale of the dataset, demonstrating the framework’s ability to maintain clustering stability in extensive corpora. A summary of the topic frequency distribution is presented in Figure 1, and representative keywords for the most frequent topics are provided in Figure 2.

Among the 266 interpretable topics, Topics 0–47 collectively accounted for 50.45% of all classified documents. Topic 0 alone represented 3.52% of the corpus, suggesting a more balanced distribution of thematic concentration compared to earlier results. The overall topic frequency distribution continues to exhibit a Zipf-like pattern, characterized by a few high-frequency topics dominating the corpus alongside a long tail of less frequent ones.

To understand the overall topic structure, the analysis focused exclusively on topics representing more than 1% of the corpus, thereby identifying the dominant domains within wellbeing research. The results, excluding noise topics, are presented in Figure 2.

An overview based on the representative keywords of each topic shows that the largest topic (3.52%) concerns *COVID-19 and pandemic-related mental health* (Topic 0), indicating

sustained scholarly attention to the psychological impacts of global crises from the perspective of wellbeing. This is followed by *Refugees and Migration* (Topic 1; 2.99%), *Dementia and Caregiving* (Topic 2; 2.48%), and *Violence and Abuse* (Topic 3; 2.30%), underscoring the continued importance of research on social vulnerability and care.

Moderate-sized topics include *Mindfulness and Stress Reduction* (Topic 4; 1.87%), *Parental and Child Wellbeing during the Pandemic* (Topic 5; 1.77%), *Oral Health* (Topic 6; 1.76%), *Indigenous Wellbeing* (Topic 7; 1.56%), *Social Media Use and Addiction* (Topic 8; 1.54%), and *Gender and Sexual Minority Health* (Topic 9; 1.39%).

Additionally, smaller yet thematically distinct topics, each accounting for approximately 1% of the corpus, were identified: *Sleep Quality* (Topic 10; 1.35%), *HIV and Stigma* (Topic 11; 1.32%), *Arts and Music Therapy* (Topic 12; 1.24%), *Nutrition and Diet* (Topic 13; 1.19%), *Autism Spectrum* (Topic 14; 1.15%), and *Maternal and Fetal Wellbeing* (Topic 15; 1.08%).

These findings objectively reaffirm that wellbeing research spans a diverse and interdisciplinary range of areas, including mental health, social inclusion, caregiving, lifestyle, development, maternal and child health, and the arts. They also demonstrate that the proposed multi-objective optimization framework enables systematic extraction and reproducible structuring of complex, multi-topic knowledge across varied social and health domains.

Figure 1. Number of topics identified and their cumulative distribution across the wellbeing-related literature corpus.

Figure 2. Representative keywords of the most frequent topics.

Topic	Count	Proportion	Representation_cleaned	Topic	Count	Proportion	Representation cleaned
0	1836	3.52%	covid19, pandemic, covid19 pandemic, mental, lockdown	70	206	0.39%	energy, environmental, economic, ewp, pollution
1	1563	2.99%	refugees, refugee, migrant, migrants, discrimination	71	204	0.39%	physical activity, physical, activity, fitness, pa
2	1293	2.48%	dementia, caregivers, care, caregiving, people dementia	72	202	0.39%	nursing, nursing students, resilience, students, nurses
3	1200	2.30%	violence, ipv, child, abuse, aces	73	197	0.38%	nature, forest, naturebased, natural, forest therapy
4	979	1.87%	mindfulness, yoga, meditation, mindfulnessbased, stress	74	196	0.38%	welfare, animals, animal, captive, animal welfare
5	927	1.77%	pandemic, covid19, children, parents, covid19 pandemic	75	195	0.37%	epilepsy, seizure, pwe, seizures, patients epilepsy
6	919	1.76%	oral, oral health, dental, caries, ohrqol	76	189	0.36%	burnout, physicians, physician, physician burnout, professional
7	815	1.56%	indigenous, aboriginal, strait, torres, torres strait	77	185	0.35%	gaming, games, game, video, esports
8	803	1.54%	media, social media, use, media use, addiction	78	180	0.34%	sentiment, tweets, twitter, social media, media
9	724	1.39%	transgender, lgbtq, gender, sexual, minority	79	179	0.34%	vaccine, vaccination, immunization, vaccines, covid19
10	706	1.35%	sleep, sleep quality, insomnia, sleep duration, sleep problems	80	176	0.34%	medical students, medical, students, student, academic
11	690	1.32%	hiv, living hiv, stigma, living, prep	81	175	0.34%	acne, skin, vitiligo, cosmetic, scars
12	648	1.24%	music, arts, art, music therapy, singing	82	175	0.34%	stroke, stroke survivors, survivors, rehabilitation, poststroke
13	620	1.19%	food, dietary, nutrition, diet, eating	83	174	0.33%	digital, internet, older, older adults, adults
14	600	1.15%	autistic, autism, asd, autism spectrum, spectrum	84	174	0.33%	bullying, victimization, cyberbullying, bullying victimization, school
15	562	1.08%	fetal, pregnancy, maternal, placental, fetal wellbeing	85	169	0.32%	climate, climate change, change, heat, extreme
16	488	0.93%	breast, reconstruction, breast reconstruction, breastq, mastectomy	86	166	0.32%	couples, marital, relationship, romantic, divorce
17	488	0.93%	cardiac, heart, heart failure, patients, failure	87	165	0.32%	cancer, parents, children cancer, childhood cancer, survivors
18	481	0.92%	postpartum, childbirth, birth, women, pregnancy	88	161	0.31%	menopause, menopausal, women, testosterone, menopausal symptoms
19	475	0.91%	diabetes, type diabetes, type, t1d, insulin	89	160	0.31%	eating, weight, pandemic, covid19, lockdown
20	471	0.90%	alcohol, use, substance, substance use, drug	90	160	0.31%	pain, opioid, surgery, postoperative, delirium
21	464	0.89%	teachers, teacher, teaching, school, job	91	159	0.30%	china, older, older adults, adults, rural
22	432	0.83%	disabilities, disability, intellectual, intellectual disability, children	92	158	0.30%	mental health, school, schools, mental, schoolbased
23	425	0.81%	app, digital, mental health, mental, apps	93	157	0.30%	religious, religiosity, spirituality, religion, spiritual
24	404	0.77%	schizophrenia, psychosis, recovery, stigma, mental illness	94	156	0.30%	homelessness, housing, homeless, experiencing homelessness, experiencing
25	396	0.76%	employees, job, employee, work, leadership	95	155	0.30%	burnout, physicians, pandemic, covid19, healthcare workers
26	388	0.74%	military, veterans, ptsd, veteran, personnel	96	154	0.29%	cows, dairy, welfare, cattle, animal
27	382	0.73%	nurses, nurse, burnout, nursing, work	97	154	0.29%	eating, eating disorder, eating disorders, nervosa, anorexia
28	364	0.70%	students, academic, university, university students, student	98	153	0.29%	water, sanitation, households, household, water insecurity
29	359	0.69%	pain, chronic pain, chronic, fibromyalgia, treatment	99	150	0.29%	cancer, exercise, cancer survivors, survivors, physical activity
30	354	0.68%	pandemic, covid19, trainees, medical, training	100	149	0.29%	cam, complementary, medicine, cancer, integrative
31	332	0.64%	hearing, hearing loss, tinnitus, cochlear, loss	101	148	0.28%	endometriosis, pain, uterine, women endometriosis, women
32	331	0.63%	workers, hcws, healthcare workers, covid19, healthcare	102	147	0.28%	cancer, patients, cancer patients, survivorship, symptom
33	330	0.63%	sport, athletes, sports, elite, athlete	103	147	0.28%	maternal, antenatal, antenatal care, anc, maternal health
34	330	0.63%	emotion, neural, regulation, emotion regulation, brain	104	145	0.28%	police, officers, police officers, firefighters, personnel
35	330	0.63%	pregnant, pregnant women, women, covid19, pandemic	105	144	0.28%	media, social media, news, social, media use
36	303	0.58%	dog, dogs, pet, owners, cats	106	144	0.28%	moral, moral distress, nurses, distress, nursing
37	303	0.58%	ecosystem, ecosystem services, land, services, ecological	107	142	0.27%	stunting, malnutrition, nutrition, nutritional, dietary
38	302	0.58%	school, adolescents, students, school climate, adolescent	108	141	0.27%	spiritual, spiritual wellbeing, cancer, spirituality, cancer patients
39	295	0.56%	ibd, bowel, inflammatory bowel, disease, bowel disease	109	141	0.27%	indoor, thermal, air, heat, comfort
40	288	0.55%	homes, residents, care, pandemic, covid19	110	141	0.27%	obesity, weight, overweight, overweight obesity, childhood obesity
41	281	0.54%	knee, hip, pain, foot, patients	111	140	0.27%	nurses, covid19, nursing, pandemic, nurse
42	281	0.54%	aging, older, age, older adults, ageism	112	140	0.27%	older, older adults, adults, india, ageing
43	280	0.54%	kidney, dialysis, hemodialysis, ckd, kidney disease	113	139	0.27%	robots, robot, ai, social robots, social robot
44	277	0.53%	long covid, covid, long, covid19, infection	114	136	0.26%	disasters, disaster, radiation, earthquake, hurricane
45	277	0.53%	prison, incarceration, correctional, incarcerated, prisoners	115	135	0.26%	body, body image, image, appreciation, body appreciation
46	276	0.53%	sexual, sexual health, dysfunction, sexuality, desire	116	135	0.26%	climate, climate change, change, climate anxiety, ecoanxiety
47	275	0.53%	residents, burnout, resident, wellness, residency	117	133	0.25%	players, load, training, soccer, training load
48	273	0.52%	loneliness, older, social, social isolation, isolation	118	133	0.25%	smoking, tobacco, cessation, smoking cessation, cigarettes
49	263	0.50%	apps, technology, technologies, dementia, older	119	133	0.25%	ai, artificial intelligence, artificial, intelligence, intelligence ai
50	259	0.50%	child, early, children, early childhood, development	120	131	0.25%	incontinence, urinary, urinary incontinence, ui, pelvic
51	252	0.48%	vision, eye, visual, glaucoma, vi	121	129	0.25%	hsct, hematopoietic, transplantation, stem cell, hematopoietic stem
52	249	0.48%	gut, microbiota, gut microbiota, microbiome, gut microbiome	122	129	0.25%	psychedelic, psychedelics, psilocybin, ayahuasca, microdosing
53	248	0.47%	physical activity, physical, activity, exercise, older	123	128	0.25%	breast cancer, breast, cancer, cancer patients, survivors
54	245	0.47%	ms, multiple sclerosis, sclerosis, multiple, pwms	124	128	0.25%	tb, tuberculosis, leprosy, la, stigma
55	245	0.47%	students, university, university students, covid19, pandemic	125	128	0.25%	air, pollution, air pollution, air quality, pm
56	245	0.47%	infertility, fertility, couples, reproductive, ivf	126	127	0.24%	nanoparticles, detection, electrochemical, biosensors, sensors
57	243	0.47%	palliative, palliative care, care, endoflife, death	127	126	0.24%	brain injury, injury, tbi, brain, abi
58	239	0.46%	work, wfh, employees, working, telework	128	125	0.24%	learning, online, students, teaching, online learning
59	238	0.46%	arthritis, ra, disease activity, jia, rheumatoid	129	124	0.24%	adolescents, parenting, parental, adolescent, parentadolescent
60	233	0.45%	violence, workplace, bullying, workplace violence, incivility	130	123	0.24%	sleep, sleep quality, covid19, insomnia, pandemic
61	232	0.44%	copd, asthma, pulmonary, chronic obstructive, obstructive pulmonary	131	122	0.23%	prostate, prostate cancer, cancer, adt, pca
62	225	0.43%	pd, parkinsons, parkinsons disease, disease, nonmotor	132	121	0.23%	financial, financial wellbeing, financial literacy, fwb, debt
63	221	0.42%	suicide, suicidal, ideation, suicidal ideation, selfharm	133	120	0.23%	employees, covid19, work, pandemic, workers
64	220	0.42%	vr, virtual, virtual reality, reality, immersive	134	120	0.23%	selfcompassion, compassion, compassionate, cft, relationship selfcompassi
65	218	0.42%	physical activity, activity, physical, pa, exercise	135	119	0.23%	menstrual, menstruation, menstrual health, girls, premenstrual
66	216	0.41%	contraceptive, marriage, women, reproductive, adolescent	136	118	0.23%	local, community, policy, assets, implementation
67	215	0.41%	compounds, antioxidant, bioactive, food, foods	137	118	0.23%	icu, intensive care, intensive, family, family members
68	213	0.41%	pharmacy, pharmacists, burnout, community pharmacists, pharmacy student	138	117	0.22%	cancer, covid19, patients, pandemic, cancer patients
69	211	0.40%	sleep, shift, sleep quality, night, fatigue	139	117	0.22%	cp, cerebral palsy, palsy, cerebral, children cp

Topic	Count	Proportion	Representation_cleaned	Topic	Count	Proportion	Representation_cleaned
140	117	0.22%	design, architectural, architecture, spaces, environment	210	74	0.14%	poultry, broiler, chickens, production, birds
141	116	0.22%	cannabis, cbd, cannabis use, use, cannabidiol	211	73	0.14%	migraine, headache, headaches, migraines, egrp
142	115	0.22%	tourism, travel, tourists, transport, cycling	212	73	0.14%	light, lighting, circadian, light exposure, daylight
143	115	0.22%	pregnancy, women, postpartum, weight, physical activity	213	73	0.14%	gambling, problem gambling, gamblers, problem, harm
144	114	0.22%	chd, congenital heart, congenital, heart disease, heart	214	72	0.14%	exercise, physical activity, activity, physical, pa
145	114	0.22%	dental, dental students, dentists, students, dentistry	215	72	0.14%	metals, water, metal, heavy, arsenic
146	114	0.22%	nurses, covid19, pandemic, frontline nurses, covid19 pandemic	216	71	0.14%	dmd, muscular, sma, dystrophy, muscular dystrophy
147	113	0.22%	older, older adults, agefriendly, housing, aging	217	71	0.14%	amputation, limb, prosthesis, lower limb, amputees
148	112	0.21%	wound, healing, tissue, hydrogel, wound healing	218	70	0.14%	sexual, sexuality, cse, sexuality education, sexual wellbeing
149	111	0.21%	psoriasis, psa, psoriatic, patients psoriasis, psoriatic arthritis	219	70	0.14%	adsorption, wastewater, removal, water, remediation
150	111	0.21%	genetic, traits, genomewide, polygenic, neuroticism	220	70	0.14%	spiritual, clergy, spirituality, workplace spirituality, workplace
151	111	0.21%	digital, parenting, mothers, postpartum, pregnancy	221	70	0.14%	musculoskeletal, musculoskeletal disorders, workrelated musculoskeletal,
152	111	0.21%	penile, sexual, vaginal, hypospadias, vulvodynia	222	70	0.14%	ties, friendship, network, networks, social
153	111	0.21%	compassion, compassion fatigue, selfcompassion, fatigue, compassion satisf	223	70	0.14%	euthymia, swemwbs, validity, mental, properties
154	110	0.21%	adhd, adhd symptoms, disorder adhd, disorder, hyperactivity	224	69	0.14%	colorectal, colorectal cancer, cancer, crc, patients
155	108	0.21%	parasites, animals, animal, spp, antimicrobial	225	69	0.14%	digital, digital health, technologies, healthcare, health
156	108	0.21%	veterinary, veterinarians, veterinary students, veterinary medicine, professic	226	68	0.14%	vaccine, vaccination, hesitancy, vaccine hesitancy, covid19 vaccine
157	107	0.20%	aging, neurodegenerative, cellular, agerelated, neuronal	227	67	0.14%	pesticides, fish, water, pesticide, aquatic
158	106	0.20%	green, greenspace, green space, space, spaces	228	67	0.14%	sexual, dating, covid19, sexual health, desire
159	105	0.20%	disabilities, intellectual, people disabilities, pandemic, covid19	229	67	0.14%	workplace, workplace health, miners, health promotion, wellness
160	104	0.20%	financial, cancer, financial toxicity, toxicity, survivors	230	67	0.14%	gardening, gardens, garden, community gardening, community
161	104	0.20%	caregivers, caregiver, cancer, burden, caregiving	231	66	0.14%	income, inequality, subjective, swb, subjective wellbeing
162	104	0.20%	sci, spinal cord, spinal, cord, cord injury	232	66	0.14%	concussion, injury, athletes, injuries, players
163	102	0.20%	sexual, cancer, cervical, cervical cancer, sexual health	233	66	0.14%	farmers, farming, agricultural, fam, farmer
164	101	0.19%	transplant, kidney, recipients, transplantation, donors	234	65	0.14%	scoliosis, lumbar, spine, surgery, spinal
165	101	0.19%	machine, fetal, machine learning, learning, prediction	235	64	0.14%	machine, machine learning, learning, prediction, accuracy
166	100	0.19%	flourishing, wellbeing, happiness, swb, positive	236	64	0.14%	personality, values, hedonic, eudaimonic, traits
167	100	0.19%	breastfeeding, milk, mothers, exclusive breastfeeding, exclusive	237	64	0.14%	tumor, drug, cells, microneedles, cancer
168	100	0.19%	abortion, miscarriage, women, pregnancy, loss	238	64	0.14%	medicaid, mothers, income, poverty, cash
169	100	0.19%	medical, medical education, medicine, professional, professionalism	239	63	0.14%	falls, fall, falling, older, fall prevention
170	98	0.19%	head neck, neck, head, neck cancer, hnc	240	63	0.14%	lifestyle, students, healthy, healthy lifestyle, habits
171	97	0.19%	cells, cancer, cell, molecular, docking	241	63	0.14%	driving, mobility, older, road, driving cessation
172	97	0.19%	sdgs, global, health, global health, sustainable	242	63	0.14%	chatbot, chatbots, conversational, cas, user
173	94	0.18%	green, nature, parks, urban, park	243	62	0.14%	cancer, survivors, app, mobile, digital
174	93	0.18%	ad, atopic, dermatitis, atopic dermatitis, skin	244	62	0.14%	workplace, mental health, employees, mental, smes
175	92	0.18%	bariatric, bariatric surgery, surgery, weight, weight loss	245	62	0.14%	fishing, fisheries, conservation, wildlife, fishers
176	92	0.18%	gut, microbiota, microbiome, gut microbiota, axis	246	62	0.14%	calves, milk, cows, colostrum, sows
177	92	0.18%	icecapa, eq5d5l, eqhwb, items, eqhwbs	247	61	0.14%	spiritual, spiritual care, spirituality, care, spiritual wellbeing
178	91	0.17%	mice, animal, rats, animals, cage	248	60	0.14%	climate, climate change, planetary, planetary health, environmental
179	90	0.17%	social prescribing, prescribing, social, sp, link workers	249	60	0.14%	food insecurity, insecurity, food, fi, food security
180	90	0.17%	cmc, children, children medical, medical complexity, parents	250	60	0.14%	housing, tenants, social housing, housing insecurity, housing tenants
181	90	0.17%	sitting, sedentary, office, office workers, workplace	251	60	0.14%	purpose, purpose life, sense purpose, sense, life
182	89	0.17%	sarscov2, viral, antiviral, virus, viruses	252	59	0.14%	fish, aquaculture, shrimp, microbiota, gut
183	88	0.17%	wearable, stress, detection, accuracy, signals	253	59	0.14%	brain, childhood, connectivity, neural, network
184	88	0.17%	als, amyotrophic lateral, amyotrophic, lateral sclerosis, mmd	254	59	0.14%	yoga, cancer, breast cancer, breast, cancer patients
185	88	0.17%	dance, dancers, dancing, older adults, older	255	58	0.14%	nutritional, cancer, cachexia, patients, malnutrition
186	86	0.16%	marine, species, ecosystem, ocean, ecosystems	256	58	0.14%	palliative, palliative care, hospice, care, burnout
187	85	0.16%	athletes, sport, sports, elite, covid19	257	58	0.14%	plastic, microplastics, plastics, mps, microplastic
188	84	0.16%	neighborhood, cohesion, neighborhood social, social cohesion, neighbourh	258	58	0.14%	inpatient, staff, mental, psychiatric, mental health
189	84	0.16%	bpd, psychotherapy, alliance, personality disorder, borderline personality	259	58	0.14%	olfactory, smell, odors, odor, olfactory dysfunction
190	83	0.16%	pcos, polycystic, ovary syndrome, polycystic ovary, ovary	260	57	0.14%	gut, microbiota, microbiome, dogs, gut microbiome
191	83	0.16%	equity, community, health equity, healthy people, health	261	57	0.14%	plant, bee, soil, plants, bees
192	83	0.16%	wound, ulcers, wounds, foot, ulcer	262	57	0.14%	alopecia, hair, aa, aga, areata
193	81	0.16%	thyroid, thyroid cancer, hypothyroidism, thyroidectomy, hypoparathyroidis	263	57	0.14%	athletes, energy, intake, energy availability, performance
194	80	0.15%	workers, resilience, healthcare, hcw, pandemic	264	57	0.14%	tw, safety health, safety, worker, osh
195	80	0.15%	gratitude, gratitude interventions, gratitude intervention, grateful, positive	265	57	0.14%	subjective, subjective wellbeing, social capital, capital, china
196	80	0.15%	ehr, electronic health, electronic, health record, record				
197	79	0.15%	pandemic, covid19, healthcare, covid19 pandemic, staff				
198	78	0.15%	epigenetic, methylation, dna methylation, dna, telomere				
199	78	0.15%	frailty, older, frail, older people, older adults				
200	78	0.15%	cancer, mindfulness, mindfulnessbased, cancer patients, patients				
201	77	0.15%	opioid, fad, substance, substance use, use				
202	76	0.15%	religious, religiosity, religious coping, faith, covid19				
203	75	0.14%	aphasia, people aphasia, speech, pwa, communication				
204	75	0.14%	horses, horse, equine, welfare, equineassisted				
205	74	0.14%	gender, community, countries, health, chw				
206	74	0.14%	weight, weight stigma, obesity, stigma, weight bias				
207	74	0.14%	mistreatment, residents, harassment, leadership, sexual harassment				
208	74	0.14%	discrimination, asian, racism, black, racial				
209	74	0.14%	nicu, neonatal, infants, parents, neonatal intensive				

To examine the structural relationships among topics derived from BERTopic modeling, we constructed a topic co-occurrence network based on topic probability matrices (Figure 3). For each document, topics with a probability of 0.02 or higher were selected; this empirically determined threshold balanced the inclusion of meaningful co-occurrences against excessive network density. Only documents containing at least five such topics were retained to ensure sufficient contextual overlap. Within these documents, all possible topic pairs were counted as co-occurrence candidates. Edge weights corresponded to the frequency of co-occurrence, and edges with fewer than 50 co-occurrences were removed to eliminate weak or spurious associations. Subsequently, isolated nodes were excluded, and betweenness centrality was computed to assess the relative structural influence of each topic. The network was visualized using the Kamada–Kawai layout, with node size scaled according to topic occurrence frequency and color intensity indicating the relative rank of centrality. Nodes with yellow–green hues denote higher centrality values, representing topics that serve as key intermediaries connecting multiple research domains within the wellbeing corpus.

Figure 3. Topic co-occurrence network of wellbeing-related literature, visualizing the structural relationships among topics based on pointwise mutual information (PMI) weighting and betweenness centrality. The network reveals three major thematic domains—public health and pandemic response, psychological and behavioral wellbeing, and social and environmental determinants—interconnected through bridging topics such as digital health technologies and occupational wellbeing. Node size represents topic frequency, and edge thickness denotes co-occurrence strength, while network layout and cluster separation highlight both central and peripheral areas of research, ensuring interpretability even in grayscale reproduction.

The co-occurrence network derived from the wellbeing corpus revealed a structured and multi-layered organization linking biomedical, ecological, and social domains. At its core, a central cluster consisting of Topic 102 (cancer survivorship), Topic 123 (breast cancer), Topic 252 (fish, aquaculture, gut microbiota), and Topic 261 (plants, bees, soil) exhibited the highest betweenness centrality. These topics function as pivotal hubs bridging medical sciences, environmental research, and biological systems. Despite originating from distinct disciplinary contexts, they converge on a shared conceptual foundation—the maintenance, adaptation, and restoration of life and health. Topics 102 and 123 emphasize the processes of recovery and quality of life among patients and survivors, whereas Topics 252 and 261 focus on ecological resilience, biodiversity, and sustainable resource systems. Their central co-occurrence suggests an emerging synthesis between human health and ecological wellbeing within the broader conceptual landscape of wellbeing research.

Surrounding this core is a cluster centered on women’s health, childbirth, and parenting, composed of Topics 168 (abortion and pregnancy loss), 18 (childbirth and postpartum), 209 (neonatal intensive care), 167 (breastfeeding), and 151 (digital parenting and postpartum support). Together, these topics delineate a continuous thematic spectrum from pregnancy to early childcare, capturing the physiological, emotional, and social dimensions of women’s wellbeing.

In the network periphery, Topic 133 (employees, COVID-19, and workplace wellbeing) emerges as an independent yet significant node, representing the growing body of research on occupational wellbeing and mental health in the context of pandemic-induced changes to work and society.

Overall, the network structure illustrates that wellbeing research is organized around interconnected layers of biomedical, environmental, and social inquiry. The strong interlinkages among core topics highlight an ongoing shift toward an integrative paradigm in which human health, ecological sustainability, and social adaptation are treated as mutually constitutive components of wellbeing. This configuration demonstrates the framework's ability to map complex interdisciplinary interdependencies through objective, interpretable, and reproducible topic structures.

Figure 4 depicts the semantic landscape of wellbeing-related research derived from topic embeddings, projected onto a two-dimensional UMAP space and subsequently analyzed through community detection. This analytical procedure yielded twenty-two semantically coherent communities (C0–C21), each representing a distinct research domain within the corpus.

As summarized in Figure 5, the communities vary substantially in size and thematic focus. The largest clusters encompass topics related to the COVID-19 pandemic (C0), nursing and occupational burnout (C1), dementia and caregiving (C2), mindfulness and meditation (C3), and aging (C4). Surrounding these central domains are smaller but conceptually meaningful clusters addressing reproductive and maternal health, sleep and mental disorders, environmental and technological interventions, and social determinants such as loneliness and homelessness.

In the visualization, node size corresponds to the relative number of documents assigned to each topic, while spatial proximity reflects semantic relatedness among communities. Taken together, these results demonstrate the multi-layered and interdisciplinary structure of wellbeing research, linking medical, psychological, and social perspectives within a unified semantic space.

Figure 4. Semantic map of wellbeing-related literature generated through UMAP projection and community detection, revealing 22 semantically coherent communities (C0–C21). The spatial configuration delineates major thematic domains—including the COVID-19 pandemic, nursing and burnout, dementia and caregiving, mindfulness and meditation, and aging—alongside smaller, specialized clusters such as reproductive and maternal health, sleep and mental disorders, technology- and nature-based wellbeing, and social vulnerability. Node size represents the number of documents associated with each topic, while community boundaries and spatial positioning indicate semantic proximity, providing a clear and interpretable representation of the multidimensional structure of wellbeing research.

Figure 5. Summary of 22 topic communities identified from wellbeing-related literature, showing the number of topics per community (C0–C21) and representative labels. The results highlight both broad domains (e.g., pandemic response, nursing and caregiving, mindfulness and aging) and specialized areas (e.g., reproductive health, digital wellbeing, environmental and social determinants), providing a structured overview of thematic diversity for decision support and knowledge discovery.

Community	Topic count	Label
C0	20	covid19, pandemic, during
C1	15	nurses, nurse, burnout
C2	14	dementia, caregivers, care
C3	13	mindfulness, yoga, meditation
C4	10	aging, older, ageism
C5	8	contraceptive, marriage, reproductive
C6	8	postpartum, childbirth, birth
C7	5	religious, religiosity, spirituality
C8	4	ms, sclerosis, pwms
C9	4	employees, job, employee
C10	3	sleep, insomnia, duration
C11	3	nature, forest, naturebased
C12	3	sexual, dysfunction, sexuality
C13	3	gut, microbiota, microbiome
C14	2	apps, technology, technologies
C15	2	climate, change, heat
C16	2	penile, sexual, vaginal
C17	2	psoriasis, psa, psoriatic
C18	2	schizophrenia, psychosis, recovery
C19	2	obesity, weight, overweight
C20	2	loneliness, solitude, isolation
C21	2	homelessness, homeless, housing

Following the community-level overview, a closer examination of each cluster reveals distinctive thematic orientations and structural relationships within the wellbeing research landscape.

The largest community (C0, 20 topics) is characterized by terms such as *covid19*, *pandemic*, and *during*, encompassing research on the multifaceted impacts of the COVID-19 crisis—including public health responses, psychosocial stress, and healthcare adaptation. Community C1 (15 topics), dominated by *nurses*, *nurse*, and *burnout*, captures the discourse on occupational stress, emotional exhaustion, and resilience among healthcare professionals. Community C2 (14 topics), defined by *dementia*, *caregivers*, and *care*, represents the expanding body of work on aging, long-term care, and the wellbeing of informal caregivers.

Community C3 (13 topics) centers on *mindfulness*, *yoga*, and *meditation*, reflecting behavioral and contemplative interventions for mental wellbeing. C4 (10 topics), associated with *aging*, *older*, and *ageism*, addresses demographic aging and the social dimensions of later

life. Closely related C5 (8 topics) and C6 (8 topics) focus on *reproductive* and *postpartum wellbeing*, respectively, emphasizing maternal health and gender-specific wellbeing outcomes.

Smaller but thematically coherent groups further enrich the corpus. C7 (5 topics) explores *religiosity* and *spirituality*, highlighting existential and moral dimensions of wellbeing. C8 (4 topics) and C9 (4 topics) concern neurological disorders and workplace wellbeing, respectively, while C10 (3 topics) links *sleep* and *insomnia* with mental health regulation. C11 (3 topics) represents *nature-based wellbeing*, focusing on restorative environmental exposure. Additional micro-clusters—C12–C21—address specialized or emerging domains, including *sexual health* (C12, C16), *gut microbiota* (C13), *digital technologies* (C14), *climate and heat stress* (C15), *chronic diseases* such as *psoriasis* (C17) and *schizophrenia* (C18), *obesity* (C19), and social vulnerabilities like *loneliness* (C20) and *homelessness* (C21).

Spatially, these communities form a coherent structure in which the large clusters (C0–C4) occupy a dense central region connecting medical, behavioral, and social research, while smaller clusters are distributed along the periphery, indicating thematic specialization and emerging subfields. The proximity between C1 (nursing) and C9 (employment) suggests a convergence around occupational wellbeing, whereas C3 (mindfulness) and C10 (sleep) delineate a behavioral intervention axis.

Collectively, these community patterns illustrate how wellbeing scholarship extends from clinical and caregiving domains toward broader psychosocial and environmental determinants. This data-driven and inductive configuration highlights the interdisciplinary and evolving nature of wellbeing research, integrating biomedical, psychological, and societal dimensions within a unified analytical framework.

5. Conclusion

This The present study introduced a multi-objective topic modeling framework designed to integrate coherence, diversity, and reproducibility optimization in the analysis of large-scale scholarly literature on wellbeing. Through the use of BERTopic with hyperparameters refined via multi-objective optimization, the approach demonstrated that interpretable and reproducible topic structures can emerge even from conceptually diverse and cross-disciplinary corpora. Its methodological significance lies not only in balancing semantic coherence with diversity but also in advancing a data-driven and inductive strategy for transparent and scalable mapping of complex research domains.

Applying this framework to a corpus of 80,040 PubMed-indexed articles produced a panoramic representation of wellbeing scholarship as an interdisciplinary and continually evolving field. The analysis identified three principal knowledge domains—medical and public health research, psychological and behavioral wellbeing, and social and environmental determinants—linked through bridging areas such as occupational wellbeing, digital health, and lifestyle interventions. Within this structural arrangement, twenty-two semantically coherent communities were observed, encompassing both established and emerging themes, including pandemic-related wellbeing, nursing burnout, dementia care, mindfulness, reproductive health, and social isolation. Collectively, these results delineate a semantic continuum connecting biological, psychological, and social dimensions within an integrated framework of human wellbeing.

In revealing this configuration, the framework elucidates the underlying logic of wellbeing scholarship. It captures the ways in which global crises, demographic transitions, and technological advances continually reshape the intellectual landscape. This finding reinforces the view that wellbeing science functions not as an isolated discipline but as a networked knowledge ecosystem, driven by the convergence of healthcare, behavioral science, and social policy.

Viewed in a broader methodological context, the framework demonstrates that multi-

objective topic modeling can operate as a rigorous, evidence-based instrument for scientific foresight and policy formulation. By delivering stable and interpretable insights into the thematic organization of research, it establishes a foundation for strategic decision-making in knowledge-intensive environments. Ultimately, this contribution advances both the epistemological understanding of wellbeing and the practical capacity for data-informed research governance.

6. Limitations and Future Work

Although BERTopic was adopted as the primary topic modeling approach, the present optimization process was bounded by a narrow set of evaluation metrics—specifically, the C_V Coherence Score, Topic Diversity Score, and a constraint on topic count. This configuration provided a workable balance between interpretability and diversity, yet it inevitably constrained the analytical scope. Expanding the metric set to include additional criteria such as topic stability, perplexity, or human-centered interpretability assessments would allow a more comprehensive foundation for hyperparameter optimization. The incorporation of stability-oriented metrics, in particular, could enhance the reliability of topic assignments and reinforce their validity for subsequent applications in knowledge discovery and decision support.

The relationship between evaluation metrics and the determination of topic quantity also presents a methodological limitation. Interpretability, thematic resolution, and the recovery of meaningful structures within the corpus are all influenced by this interaction. Evidence from the present analysis—namely, the identification of multiple large-scale clusters in the co-occurrence network and their decomposition into 22 communities through UMAP-based clustering—illustrates how parameter configurations directly shape the granularity of the resulting topic space. Conducting systematic sensitivity analyses would therefore clarify these dependencies and improve both the robustness and generalizability of the framework. Such refinement is essential for ensuring that large-scale analyses remain not only methodologically sound but also practically relevant to research and technology policy design.

Advancing this line of work requires both quantitative and qualitative extensions. Cross-validation procedures could be introduced to test the stability of topic distributions across subsamples, while expert-based evaluation—where domain specialists judge conceptual coherence, disciplinary relevance, and applicability—would provide complementary verification. A combined approach linking expert assessment with quantitative optimization would maintain interpretability and objectivity, ensuring actionable outcomes for policy and funding stakeholders. Furthermore, the inclusion of network-derived indicators such as centrality and modularity at the community level could establish a more integrated criterion for topic quality assessment.

Through such methodological broadening, multi-objective optimization frameworks could evolve into robust instruments for large-scale literature analysis and decision support. In practical terms, this would enable the continuous monitoring of emerging research domains, the strategic allocation of resources, and the anticipation of scientific and technological trajectories. Strengthening these dimensions would consolidate the framework's position as an analytical foundation for policy formation, research management, and foresight activities in knowledge-intensive environments.

Acknowledgements

The authors did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors for this research.

References

- Abusitta, A., Otrok, H., Mizouni, R. and Singh, S. (2024) 'A survey on explainable artificial intelligence: From foundations to applications', *Expert Systems with Applications*, 234, 121044. doi:10.1016/j.eswa.2023.121044.
- Al Azher, I., Seethi, V.D.R., Akella, A.P. and Alhoori, H. (2025) 'LimTopic: LLM-based topic modeling and text summarization for analyzing scientific articles limitations', *Proceedings of the 24th ACM/IEEE Joint Conference on Digital Libraries (JCDL '24)*, Article No. 30, pp. 1–12.
- Devlin, J., Chang, M.W., Lee, K. and Toutanova, K. (2019) 'BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding', *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies (Volume 1)*, pp. 4171–4186. doi:10.18653/v1/N19-1423.
- Egger, R. and Yu, J. (2022) 'A topic modeling comparison between LDA, NMF, Top2Vec, and BERTopic to demystify Twitter posts', *Frontiers in Sociology*, 7, 886498. doi:10.3389/fsoc.2022.886498.
- Farea, A., Tripathi, S., Glazko, G. and Emmert-Streib, F. (2024) 'Investigating the optimal number of topics by advanced text-mining techniques: Sustainable energy research', *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 136, 108877. doi:10.1016/j.engappai.2024.108877.
- Grootendorst, M. (2024) 'BERTopic: Parameter tuning'. Available at: https://maartengr.github.io/BERTopic/getting_started/parameter%20tuning/parametertuning.html (Accessed: 18 July 2025).
- Huang, A.Y., Zhang, D. and Zhou, X. (2023) 'Word embeddings for topic modeling: An application to economic policy uncertainty index estimation', *Expert Systems with Applications*, 211, 118517. doi:10.1016/j.eswa.2022.118517.
- Inoue, Y. (2025, August 27). 'Multi-objective optimization of BERTopic for large-scale scholarly literature analysis: Application to autoregressive models', SSRN. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5409922>
- Medvecki, D., Bašaragin, B., Ljajić, A. and Milošević, N. (2024) 'Multilingual transformer and BERTopic for short text topic modeling: The case of Serbian', arXiv preprint, arXiv:2402.03067. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.03067>.
- Panagoulas, G., Koukopoulos, D., Koukopoulos, Z. and Martakos, D. (2024) 'A novel framework for AI explainability in decision support systems', *Expert Systems with Applications*, 235, 121238. doi:10.1016/j.eswa.2023.121238.
- Park, S., Lee, H. and Kim, J. (2024) 'Automatic topic discovery and forecasting of process mining research', *Expert Systems with Applications*, 227, 120164. doi:10.1016/j.eswa.2023.120164.
- Pavithra, C.B. and Savitha, J. (2024) 'Topic modeling for evolving textual data using LDA, HDP, NMF, BERTopic, and DTM with a focus on research papers', *Journal of Technology and Informatics*, 5(2).
- Sun, Y.H., Sun, Y., Wang, J. and Xu, C. (2025) 'Topic mining and evolution trend analysis of FinTech research based on the BERTopic model', SSRN preprint, pp. 1–29. doi:10.2139/ssrn.5139578.
- Yu, C. and Xiang, Z. (2023) 'Discovering topics and trends in artificial intelligence research: An LDA-based approach', *Expert Systems with Applications*, 211, 118611. doi:10.1016/j.eswa.2022.118611.